

ATTACHMENT 2

Communication Outputs

The CRA analysis is considered a crucial step towards climate change adaptation of the Žilina region. ŽSK has informed about initial phases of the project via social media as well as press releases. ŽSK has used web portals www.zilinskazupa.sk, www.hrajzakraj.sk and respective FB accounts. Press releases are sent to regional / national media to reach wider audience:

Communication outputs, having been issued so far:

- on 7th April 2025, ŽSK published the information on joining CLIMAAX group via successful applying for second call, describing generally the project, its possible outcomes and new as well as previous members of the initiative:

WEB site: [Skupina CLIMAAX sa rozrástla. Pripojil sa Žilinský kraj. – Žilinský kraj HrajZaKraj](#)

FB: [Hraj ZA kraj - SKUPINA CLIMAAX SA ROZRÁSTLA O ŽILINSKÝ... | Facebook](#)

FB: (repeated on 7th May 2025 [SKUPINA CLIMAAX SA ROZRÁSTLA... - Žilinský Samosprávny Kraj | Facebook](#))

- on 11th August 2025, the press release on further development of the project was publicized, containing description of workflows and their utilisation in the region, contribution of the established Expert group. Press release was widely cited by regional as well as national media:

Web site: [Žilinský kraj mapuje klimatické hrozby. Pomôžu mu európske dáta aj špičková metodika - ŽSK](#)

Web site: [Žilinský kraj mapuje klimatické hrozby. – Žilinský kraj HrajZaKraj](#)

FB: [ŽILINSKÝ KRAJ SA PRIPRAVUJE NA... - Žilinský Samosprávny Kraj | Facebook](#)